

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Public relations and corporate image: a study of MTN and GLO Nigeria, Calabar

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Abstract

This study set out specifically to assess the role of public relations in corporate image, with particular focus on MTN and GLO, Calabar. The study was anchored on psychodynamic and socio-cultural theories. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher adopted survey method of fact finding with the questionnaire as instrument for data collection. A sample of 384 respondents for the study was determined by the Check Market Sample Calculator. Therefore, sample size of 384 respondents was drawn from the population of 375,196. While multistage sampling approach was employed in the selection of actual respondents. The study employed simple percentage frequency table in analysing responses from the questionnaire, Population T-test and Simple Linear Regression in testing the hypotheses. Linear regression is a statistical method for obtaining a formula to predict values of one variable from another where there is a casual relationship between the two variables. The method was used to test the relationship between public relations and corporate image. It was discovered that the activities of public relations have led to increase in the profit of MTN and GLO, it was also discovered amongst others that the level of corporate development of the mobile companies is significantly high. It was recommended that public relations practitioners/professionals of GLO and MTN, Calabar should intensify and sustain the application of public relations strategies in achieving organizational objectives. It was also recommended that GLO and MTN telecommunication companies should periodically appraise their public relations practices at various levels of their corporate organizational operations and such appraisals should be made public so as to encourage other organizations to imbibe the public relations culture as a panacea for corporate development amongst others.

Keywords; Corporate Image; Public Relations; G. S. M. Subscribers; Market; Multi- Media Messaging

1. Introduction

The dynamic, unstable and unpredictable state of the business environment and the attendant volatile nature of sustainability of corporate entities, occasioned by high level of competition and technological advancement has led to the recent increase in the number of failed corporate entities in different sectors of most economies of the world.

Task oriented approach for example is a management style of performance where management focuses more on tasks that need to be performed in order to meet certain goals or to achieve performance standard. These leaders are typically less concerned with the idea of catering for employees but rather more concerned with finding the step-by-step solution required to meet specific goals. They will often actively define the work and the roles required, put structures in place, and plan, organize and monitor progress within the team. The advantage of task oriented management style is that it ensures that deadlines are met and jobs are completed and it is useful for team members who do not manage their time well. (Ricky, 2010)

The human relations management style on the other hand focuses on satisfaction, motivation and general well-being of team members. This management style encourages good team work and collaboration, through fostering positive

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relationship and good communication. Relationship-oriented leaders prioritize the welfare of everyone in the group and place time and effort in meeting the individual needs of everyone involved. This may involve offering incentives like bonuses, providing mediating role to deal with workplace or classroom conflicts, having more casual interactions with team members to learn about their strength and weaknesses, creating a non-competitive and transparent work environment. (Ricky, 2010)

This scenario automatically places demand on corporate organizations to seek out ways of survival and sustainability of its corporate growth and development. Several strategic and alternative measures have been tried in order to come out of the turbulent water of the business environment. Suddenly, there seems to be a shift from task oriented approach to human relation approach, public relations serves as an antidote to greater business achievement (Theaker 2001).

It is widely accepted that the aim of any business organization is to achieve growth, increase in turn over, assets and profit. But all of these are dependent on the goodwill of the organization's various publics. Goodwill according to Crossman (2016), is secured not so much as a result of the organization's mere existence but as the sustained strategic planning, execution and evaluation of the perception of their publics in relation to the organization.

Every organization no matter how large or small ultimately depends on its reputation for survival and success. Customers, suppliers, employees, investors, journalist and regulators can have a powerful impact on an organization, they all have opinion about the organization they come in contact with whether good or bad, right or wrong, and these perceptions will drive their decision about whether they want to work with, shop with and support these organizations. (Theaker 2001).

In today's competitive market, reputation can be a company's biggest asset; the thing that makes you stand out from the crowd and gives you a competitive edge. Effective public relations can help manage reputation, communication and building good relationship with the organization stakeholders. (Nwosu, 2005)

Public relations is a discipline about reputation. The result of what you do, say and what others say about you. In this interdependent world, it is really important for almost every kind of organizations to keep a long term and trustworthy relations with the communities or public in order to handle the up-coming challenges and to maintain their survival and success. The field of public relations is all about developing, understanding and building good relationship with the various publics including government, media, employees, investors, suppliers, customers etc. The worth of public relations in any organization cannot be overlooked. This is largely dependent on the fact that public relations unit of an organization is a crucial factor in deciding the success of any organization by developing and fostering its corporate image. (Nwosu, 2005)

Whether a company is the hunter or the prey, a strong corporate image can have a profound impact on both short term financial results and long term corporate image. It is widely accepted that the aim of any business organization is to achieve growth, increase in turn over, assets and profit. But all of this is dependent on the goodwill of the organization's various publics. Goodwill according to Crossman (2016) is secured not so much as a result of the organization's mere existence but as the sustained strategic planning, execution and evaluation of the perception of their publics in relation to the organization.

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This research work intends to study Public Relations and Corporate Image with particular focus on MTN and GLO Nigeria, Calabar. The study was to ascertain the extent of awareness and effectiveness of communication strategy generated as a result of their public relations effort. These efforts consequently will certainly reflect on company's profit, market share, workers welfare, social responsibility, mutual understanding and good-will which are essential for corporate image. The extent to which the above cardinal objectives are vigorously achieved is a self-fulfilling prophecy of the extent of corporate image (Anyoogu 2006). The result of this research will assist corporate organizations to make vital decision on issues of management and to understand the place of Public Relations in any organization.

The digital Global System of Mobile Communication, popularly known as GSM came into existence in Nigeria when the Nigerian communication commission licensed three firms to start the GSM business in 2001. The companies are: MTN, Econet (now Airtel), and MTEL a subsidiary of NITEL which successfully switched on their Networks on August 8, 2001.

The three companies pioneered the GSM business, with Globacom joining the race two years later. Thus, MTN Limited was incorporated in February 2001 and started operation on May 16, 2001 with its Head Office in Lagos State Nigeria. (Anyaogu, 2006).

1.1. Statement of the Problem

The place of public relations in organisations like MTN and GLO Nigeria cannot be overemphasized as it fosters the relationship between an organization and its publics.

In May, 2001 and August, 2003 MTN and GLO Nigeria were granted licences to operate as telecommunication companies in Nigeria, each of the licences came with a guide intended to guide the operations of these telecommunication companies. Also, the guides contain fines attached for any defaulter.

Comparatively, the growth and expansion of MTN and GLO Nigeria have been tremendous of recent, both in capital, subscribers and area of coverage but they have been faced with various challenges which resulted to paying fines to the Nigerian government. Some of the fines paid by MTN were as a result of poor network or service, excessive tax claims, unpaid taxes and the most recent one which is the Subscriber Identity Module (SIM) infraction fine, while fines paid by GLO were as a result of forcefully subscribing customers to data and the SIM infraction fine. The question on the minds of many is what role have the public relations units of MTN and GLO played that have led to the two paying fines at all or paying less compared to each other? The aim of this study is to investigate the role of public relations in the corporate image of MTN compared to GLO, particularly in Calabar.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to:

- Determine whether Public Relations has any impact on corporate development of MTN and GLO, Calabar.
- Ascertain whether public relations guarantees increase in profit of the MTN and GLO, in Calabar as a form of corporate development.
- Ascertain the level of awareness in the use of public relations for corporate Development of MTN and GLO, in Calabar.
- Determine the effectiveness of public relations strategies used by MTN and GLO, Calabar for corporate development by the company in Calabar.

1.2. Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide this study:

- What role does public relations play in corporate image of MTN compared to GLO, Calabar?
- To what extent does public relations guarantee increase in profit of MTN compared to GLO Calabar?
- What is the public relations strategy used for the corporate image of MTN compared to GLO, Calabar?
- what is the level of awareness of the use of public relations by MTN compared to GLO, Calabar?

1.3. Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses have been formulated to guide this study:

- The level of corporate development of network companies (Glo and MTN) is not significantly high.
- The Role of Public relations in network companies does not significantly predict their corporate development.
- There is no significant difference in corporate of Glo and MTN as opined by their lovers.

1.4. Theoretical Framework

The researcher considered the psychodynamic and socio-cultural theories as most suitable theoretical framework for this study.

1.5. Psychodynamic Theory

Psychodynamic theory was propounded in 1900 by Sigmund Freud. The theory holds that for a persuasive message to be considered effective, it must succeed in altering the psychological functioning of the recipient(s) in such a way that he/she or they will respond overtly to the model of behaviour suggested by the communicator. For example, to

encourage enlightened voting behaviour, the communicator would have to get people to develop favourable attitudes to the electoral process as a whole. The psychological motivations used as intervening variables between the message stimulus and audience response include hunger, sexual urge, status drive, opinion, et cetera.

The study of motivation and mental processes is the foundation of the theory. The psychodynamic theory state that bad behaviour can be changed through the breaking of bad habit. Specifically, the major assumptions of the psychodynamic theory are as follows:

The psychodynamic approach also looks at mental process. However, the cognitive approach does not explain what motivate behaviour. Issues of motivation are central within the psychodynamic approach, which are biologically based.

Concerns about motivation are linked to the psychology of personality, since intentions are held by someone. Thus, the theory of personality is also central.

The psychodynamic approach focuses on the role of internal processes. It focuses on the person as a whole.

Fundamental assumption is psychic determinism, which states that all behaviour have a cause (determined) and the cause is to be found in the mind.

Much of behaviour is governed by a process that lays outside the individual's awareness that is the consciousness.

Moreover, to tie the psychodynamic theory to this study entails that public relations objective is to maintain an organizational image. Therefore, to be able to change the public's mind set from negative to positive, the public relations officers would require well packaged and persuasive information or message that will be able to change the aggrieved psyche of the public.

1.6. The Socio Cultural Theory

The Socio Cultural Theory was propounded by Lev Vygotsky in 1934 seeks to explain the way in which variables such as organizational membership, work roles and reference groups, exercise social control and help to shape the attitude of the people in ways that they will depart from their own internal disposition. The theory considers human development as a socially mediated process in which children acquire their cultural values, beliefs and problem-solving strategies through collaborative dialogue with more knowledgeable members of the society.

Lev Vygotsky theory stress the fundamental role of social interaction in the development of cognition. He believes strongly that the community plays a central role in the process of making meaning. The socio cultural theory emphasizes of the following factors which enhances cognitive process:

- Culture affecting cognitive development
- Social factor affecting cognitive development
- Role of language in cognitive development
- Adults as important sources of cognitive development

The relevance of this theory to this study is that public relations relate socially with its publics through this relationship, they interact. Their interaction helps them to know what gift, message or information and programme that will appeal to them. Also, professional communications with their knowledge of the public through socialization and constant interaction and research should know the type of message to put forward that will heal the wounds of the public who have already considered the organization as bad and turned their back against it to rethink through the influence of the message and return to the organization.

1.7. Conceptual and Literature of Related Review

The researcher examined some of the principles and concepts that are important or relevant to the study. The researcher examined what public relations is and what it is not, based on the understanding of a layman and the societal misconception as being practice in most organizations today. The study will also highlight some models that may find numerous applications to the study of public relations and models that were propounded by several authorities in public relations. Information on this subject matter were derived from past work done on the subject matter. Encyclopedia, text books from different authors, journals, periodicals, magazines, Newspapers and the Internet. They are known as external secondary data. If the information is obtained internally through some historical data, it is known as internal secondary data and is used as a base for field work which is a field survey. These field surveys generate new information

known as primary data. The chapter has been organized as follows: Review of concepts, review of studies and theoretical framework.

1.8. Definition of Public Relations

Defining public relations has not been easy as most authors have tried to define the concept 'Public Relations', each emphasizing a slightly different approach and another attempting to arrive at a simple, brief and accurate definition. The difficulty in developing a single acceptable definition reflects the complexity and diversity of the profession.

For the purpose of this study, few definitions were considered.

British Institute of Public Relations defines Public Relations as a planned and sustained effort to establish and maintain good will and mutual understanding between an organization and its publics. (British Institute of Public Relation, 1987).

Ben and Nnanyelugo (1999) defined public relations as a management function which evaluates public attitudes, identifies the policies and procedures of an individual organization with public interest, plans and executes programmes of action to earn public understanding and acceptance.

Frank (1982) argued that Public Relations is all forms of planned communication, outward and inward, between an organization and its publics for the purpose of achieving specific objectives concerning mutual understanding. Webster Dictionary (2019) defines it as the promotion of rapport and goodwill between a person, firm or institution, other people, special public or the community at large through the distribution of comparative materials in the development of neighborly interchange and assessment of public reaction.

Osuji (1990) saw public relations as the art and science of analyzing trend, practicing the consequences, counselling organization's leadership and plan programme of action which will serve both an organization and the public interest.

World assembly of public relations professionals in Mexico (1978) defined Public relations as the art and social science of analysing trends, predicting their consequences, counseling organization leaders, and implementing planned programmes of action which will serve both the organization and the public interest.

Nwosu and Uffor (2005) defined public relations as an art and science of building and sustaining a credible reputation for any organization Black (1990) opined that the fundamental purpose of public relations is to establish mutual understanding based on true knowledge and full information.

Having considered the various definitions stated above, one may still have a blurred view of the concept of public relations if we fail to examine the statement of public relations by Public Relations Society of America (PRSA) 1982, as articulated by Hendrix (2001). According to him, public relations helps our complex, private society to reach decision and function more effectively by contributing to mutual understanding among groups and institutions. It serves to bring private and public policies into harmony.

1.9. The Concepts of Publics in Public Relations

Publics can be defined as everyone interested in an organization, affected by that organization's policies, decisions, interest, communication or project and whose needs, wants, actions or opinions, and attitudes can affect the organization and differs from one organization to the other (Nwosu, 2005). He added that one way to further understand the publics of an organization is to see them as the internal and external stakeholders of the organization. The stakeholders differ depending on the organization.

He further argued that there are many ways of classifying publics of an organization. The most popular is to group them into two internal and external publics.

Internal publics are those publics that have more enduring stake in the organization such as employees, customers, suppliers, shareholders, financial institutions, etc. These set of publics have a direct stake on the organization and require serious attention. While external publics on the other hand are those publics that interact with the organization but do not have a direct relationship with the organization and require less attention. Organizational publics can further be classified into primary, secondary, and tertiary publics.

Primary publics are those that need the first attention. (Nwosu, 2005) While tertiary publics are those that require last attention. Nwosu's further classification include:

1.10. Basic and Special Publics

The basic or fundamental publics for a target group can be external or internal. So also can special publics who require and deserve special public relations actions, communications, attend policies and decision from the organization (Nwosu, 2005). The term corporate identity and corporate image are sometimes confused with each other. Corporate identity is what the organization communicates (either intentionally or un-intentionally) through various cues, whereas its image is how its publics actually view it.

An image is a perception and exists only in the mind of a receiver (Theaker 2001). To formulate an image, publics interpret identity in a wider context with broader frames of reference. Practically, organizations cannot construct a corporate image because they cannot control the context in which their communication is received, interpreted or understood.

Nevertheless, a clear, well managed corporate identity can go some way to affecting a strategically important image. A neglected corporate identity may send out all the wrong messages. Theaker (2001) opined that an organization may commonly assume that it only communicate when it wants to but unfortunately, for many companies, a failure to control communication result in confused image.

1.11. Review of Studies

Many related studies have been conducted by scholars on public relations and corporate development. Although these studies do not have the same title but they tend to focus on the role of public relations on corporate development. Some of these studies as considered in this study are treated below:

1.12. The Importance of Public Relations in Corporate Sustainability

Rivero and Theodore (2014), carried out a study titled 'The importance of Public Relations in Corporate Sustainability'. With the aim to present the importance of using public relations to communicate the intent and application of corporate sustainability by organizations that are involved in the practice. The authors posited that public relations must be embraced by organizations that follow the corporate sustainability model. From an internal/external perspective, stakeholders, employees and the public must communicate effectively, efficiently and on a timely basis in order to enhance their positive interaction and attain the desired goal.

They concluded that the role of the corporation within its internal environment is to respect under ethical and legal auspices, respect the equity between work and compensation/benefit, and implant motivational forces that need to increase human resources, work satisfaction and development within its structure.

1.13. The Role of Public Relations in Promoting Government Development Programmes: A Study of Microfinance Support Center Ltd Kampala

In another related conducted by Narasi, (2016), titled, 'The Role of Public Relations in Promoting Government Development Programmes: A study of Microfinance Support Centre Limited and other Government Development Programme, focusing on Microfinance support centre limited Kampala. Using three data collection tools i.e questionnaire, key informant interview and secondary data source revealed that campaigns, lobbying, propaganda, professional ethics and corporate social responsibility as public relations practice while product promotion, special event management, crisis management and managing adverse publicity were cited as means of integrating policy coverage of government activities and increasing the internal cohesion of the agency found to be the effects of public relations.

1.14. Assessment of Public Relations Impact in the Development of Corporate Image: A Study of Glo, Calabar.

In a study conducted by Odey (2014), titled 'Assessment of Public Relations Impact in the Development of Corporate Image: A study of GLO, Calabar'. With the aim to identify the major roles played by public relations in the sustenance of corporate image of Glo, Calabar. Using survey method of fact finding and questionnaire as an instrument of data collection. It discovered that public relations contribute positively in projecting a favourable image of an organization. The researcher recommend among others that adequate training should be given to Glo, Calabar public relations staff to enable them meet the demands of modern communication technologies. Odey focussed more on the role of public relations in an organization, he tried to outline their functions and proffered possible ways to further enhance these functions.

1.15. Analysis of Public Relations as a Tool for Corporate Development: A Study of MTN, Enugu

In a study conducted by Maduabuchi (2006), titled 'Analysis of Public Relations: As a Tool for Corporate Development: A study of MTN Nigeria, Enugu, was to ascertain the extent at which Public relations influence the increase in company profit; influence on social responsibility; enhance good customer relation impact on the brand image; how effective the communication tools are used. Using questionnaire, oral interview and observation as data gathering instruments. The researcher found among others that public relations is a tool for corporate development and recommend that public enlightenment campaign should be intensified to create awareness on the use of public relations to achieve organizational objectives.

From the reviews, we found that Orlando and Theodore, (2014), focussed on public relations as what should embrace by corporate sustainability model. From an internal external perspective, stakeholder, employees and public must communicate efficiently and on a timely basis in order to enhance their positive interaction and attain the desired goal of the organization.

Narasi, (2016), on the other hand saw campaigns lobbying, propaganda, professional ethics and corporate social responsibility as public relations practice while product promotion, special event management crisis managing adverse publicity were cited as means of integrating policy coverage of organizations activities and increases the internal cohesion of found to be the effects of public relations.

Maduabuchi (2006), is of the same view with the position of Narasi. He looked at the overall productivity and efficiency of an organization to depend of the effectiveness of the use of public relations strategy, good customer relations, corporate social responsibility, enlightenment campaigns, customer relations etc. are important tools which if effectively utilized can lead to increase in an organization's overall productivity level.

While Odey focussed more on the role of public relations in an organization, he tried to outline their functions and proffered possible ways to further enhance these functions.

However, the lacuna that has been discovered by the researcher of this study which the previous studies did not address adequately is the attitude by staff of an organization which can lead to poor performance of the organization. This is because the staff of any organization are the last link between the organization and its public. This is the basis for this present study titled: Public Relations and Corporate Development: A Study of MTN and GLO, Calabar.

The focus should not only be on what an organization can do to retain and attract customers but also, on what the staff of the organization is doing to attract and maintain existing customers as it concern their overall behaviour.

1.16. Research Design

Research design is a conceptual blue-print within which research is conducted or guide for generating primary data. (Shoken 2016).

The research design for this study is the survey method of quantitative research. For data collection, this method provides a means of measuring a population's characteristics, self – reporter and observed behavior, awareness of programmes, attitudes or opinions and needs. (Shoken 2016). The design will involve the selection of a sample to represent the entire population. Unlike a census, where all member of a population are studied, a sample in a survey gathers information from only a portion of a population of interest.

Wimmer and Dominick (2011) opined that the descriptive survey method attempts to picture or document current conditions or attitudes. I.e. to describe what exist at the moment. This method as adopted employs questionnaire as the instrument, which makes it most relevant and most respondent. Also, in-depth interview was used as instruments for data collection.

1.17. Area of Study

The research area of this study is Calabar. Calabar is the capital of Cross River State. For the purpose of administration, the city is divided into Calabar Municipality and Calabar South Local Government Areas. It has 22 wards with an area of 406 square kilometer (157 sq metre) and a population of 375196 (Cross River National Population Commission, 2019).

Calabar is a tourism capital of Nigeria and a port city in southern part of Nigeria, near the Cameroon border. It sits on a hill near Calabar River and the Cross River Delta. British architecture fills the city's older sections, including: Henshaw Town, Duke Town and the waterfront area.

Calabar has three principal landlord kingdoms, namely: the Qua kingdom of Ejagham (Ekoi)/Bantu origin, the Efut and the Efik Kingdoms. The Qua kingdom has the Ndidem of the Qua nation as Grand patriarch, and the Efuk Kingdom have the Muri Munene as Grand patriarch and the Efik kingdom patriarch is the Obong.

Calabar Municipality is bounded by Odukpani Local Government Area in the North-east by great Kwa River, in the South by Calabar River and Calabar South Local Government. It has an area of 331.551 square kilometers with a population of 183,681 (Cross River National Population Commission, 2019).

Two ethnic groups of Quas and the Effiks form the indigenous population of the area. By virtue of its location along the water front fishing and trade are its occupation identified with them. The Quas on the other hand occupy the bulk of the hinterland of Calabar where farmers, hunters, traders and blacksmiths are found. Calabar South on the other hand is one of the local government areas of cross river state Nigeria. It has 12 wards with its administrative headquarters located in Anantigha town, bounded by Akpabuyo in the west, Calabar Municipality in the North, the Calabar River in south and east with a population of 191,515 people. (Cross River National Population Commission, 2019).

1.18. Population of the Study

The following constituted the population of the study:

- The employees of MTN and GLO.
- The dealers on MTN and GLO products/services.
- The customers of MTN and GLO services

It is from these population segment that the sample elements were drawn.

1.19. Sampling Size and Technique

Wimmer and Dominick (2011), define a sample as a subset of the population that is a representative of the entire population. To determine the sample size for this study, the researcher used Check Market Sample Calculator. This system is used to calculate the number of respondents to get statically from a specific population. To achieve is, the researcher calculates the margin of error based on the population size. Therefore, using 5 percent margin of error and 95 percent confidence level, a sample size of 384 was drawn from a population of 375,196.

In considering the sample size for this research work, the research took notice of the fact that three groups of the population of MTN and GLO are involved; the staff, subscribers and dealers of the companies' products. The sample were drawn from MTN and GLO head offices and dealers cutting across Calabar Municipality and Calabar South Local Government Areas and sample size statically consisting of 384 respondents were drawn from 48 streets in Calabar.

The researcher used a multistage approach for this study. In the view of Crossman (2019) Multistage approach is a non-probability technique wherein the sampling is carried out in several stages such that the sample size gets reduced at each stage. Purposive sampling also known as judgmental, selective or subjective sampling, is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their study. Cluster sampling may be used when it is either impossible or impractical to compile an exhaustive list of the elements that make up without a target population. As part of the sampling procedure to select 384 respondents, simple random sampling was also adopted. Simple Random Sampling is a subset of sample chosen from a larger set or population, each set is chosen randomly and entirely by chance such that each individual or set has the same probability or chance of being selected at any stage during the sampling process. Systematic sampling was also deployed to select 8 samples from each of the 48 streets selected. Systematic sampling is a type of probability sampling method in which sample members from a larger population are selected according to a random starting point but with a fixed periodic interval. The aforementioned sampling technique and procedure were employed by the researcher for this study as it allows for easy management of survey, reduce cost and waste of time.

In the next stage, cluster sampling was deployed to group Calabar into streets, Calabar Municipality was grouped into 52 streets. The third stage introduced the simple random sampling through ballot system where 52 streets of Calabar municipality were written on separate pieces of paper folded into a container, thoroughly mixed together and 23 of them were picked. The same system applied to select the 25 streets from Calabar South. The fourth stage introduced

the systematic sampling procedure was used after the first house was arbitrarily selected, one respondent was selected from every fifth house on the selected street. In a situation where there is no person was found in the fifth house, the next house was automatically selected. This was repeated till the required number of respondents were selected from every street.

1.20. Instrument of Data Collection

The instruments of data collection for this study were the structured questionnaire and in-depth interview with key informants. The structured questionnaire was structured with closed-ended items which were in a form of Likert scale format of strongly agreed represented by (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed with (D) and Strongly Disagreed with (SD) which measured the degree of response to the various sections required. Five questions were structured directed to the staff of MTN and GLO which constituted segments of the population for this study while the in-depth interview contained open-ended questions. The questionnaire was divided into two parts; part A and B. part A focused on the demographic data while section B covered the remaining questions answered by the three sections of the research publics. The two parts combined to help analyze the research questions and test research hypotheses raised for the study. Some of the questionnaire items were set in the dichotomous (yes or no) format. The in-depth- interview with key informants was used to support the findings from the questionnaire.

1.21. Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

Validity is the extent to which an instrument accurately measures what it set out to measure. The researcher presented the instrument to an expert in measurement and research who carefully scrutinized it and effected all the necessary corrections and adjudged it was valid.

The reliability of the instrument was Cronbach Alpha Reliability Estimation Method. To ensure that the instrument measured consistently what it purported to measure, a trial test was carried out on forty (40) network users. The network users involved in the trial test were not part of the study population, though share the same characteristics. The data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha Reliability method which yielded reliability coefficient ranging from .628 to .890.

The Alpha coefficient so obtained were considered good enough to render the instrument reliable in measuring what it purported to measure. The results of this reliability test are shown in

Table 1 Cronbach Alpha Reliability Estimates of Research Instrument (N = 40)

S/N	Variable	No. Of Items	_N	Sd	Reliability
1	Level of awareness of my Network Calabar in the use of Public Relations	5	16.525	3.896	0.890
2	Corporate Development	5	13.925	2.566	0.628
3	Importance of role played by my Network staff	5	16.225	3.324	0.816
4	Level of contribution by Public Relations	5	17.050	3.328	0.867
5	Role of Public Relations	5	14.575	2.601	0.686

1.22. Method of Data Collection

Data were collected with the help of two assistants. The two assisted the researcher in administering copies of the questionnaire. The researcher himself concentrated on the in-depth interview with the key informants with the use of phone recording devices.

Method of Data Analysis

The study employed Population T – test and Simple Linear Regression in analyzing the data.

T-test is a type of inferential statistic used to determine if there is a significant difference between the means of two groups which may related in certain features. While Simple Linear Regression is a statistical method for obtaining a formula to predict values of one variable from another where there is a casual relationship between the two variable.

1.23. Data Presentation and Analysis from the Questionnaire

Table 2 Gender Distribution and Mobile Preference

Gender	Distribution of respondents	Percentage
Male	215	57.5
Female	154	42.5
Total	374	100.0
Network Preference	Distribution of Respondents	Percentage
MTN	271	72.6
GLO	103	27.4
Total	374	100.0

Source: field work 2020

Table 2 combined to present question 1 and 2. It shows that majority of the respondents (215 representing 57.6 percent) were males. In terms of network bias, majority of respondents (271 representing 72.6 percent) chose MTN.

Table 3 Distribution of respondents' sources of network satisfaction

Network	Distribution of respondents	Percentage
Calls	209	59.9
Data	141	37.7
Text Message	24	6.4
Total	374	100.0

Source: field work 2020

Table 3 Shows that majority of the respondents (209 representing 59.9 percent) derive their source of network satisfaction from calls, 141 respondents representing 37.7 percent derive their network satisfaction from data and 24 respondents representing 6.4 percent derive their network from text message.

Table 4 Respondents' relationship between their preferred network and subscribers/dealers

Survey statement	Degree of response	Percentage	
There exist a very smooth relationship between my preferred network and the subscribers/dealers	SA	134	35.8
	A	187	50.0
	D	43	11.4
	SD	10	2.6
Total		374	100.0

Source: field work, 2020

Table 4. shows that majority of respondents (134 representing 35.8 percent and 187 respondents representing 50.0 percent) strongly agreed and agreed respectively that there exist a very smooth relationship between their preferred network and the subscribers/ dealers while (43 respondents representing 11.4 and 10 representing 2.6 percent) respectively disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that there exist a very smooth relationship between their preferred network and the subscribers/dealers.

Table 5 Respondents' opinion on the image of the networks among subscribers/dealers

Survey statement	Degree of response	Percentage
The image of my network is highly esteemed among its subscribers/ dealers	SA 150	40.1
	A 169	45.2
	D 49	13.1
	SD 6	1.6
Total	374	100.0

Source: field work, 2020

Table 5 indicates that majority of the respondents (150 respondents representing 40.1 percent) and (169 respondents representing 45.2 percent) strongly agreed and agree that the image of their network is highly esteemed among its subscribers/dealers, while (49 respondents representing 13.1 percent and 6 respondents representing 1.6 percent) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that the image of their network is highly esteemed among its subscribers/dealers.

Table 6 Respondents level of trust in their networks

Survey statement	Degree of response	Percentage
My network has won the mind of its subscribers/dealers	SA 159	42.5
	A 154	41.2
	D 48	12.2
	SD 13	3.5
Total	374	100.0

Source: field work, 2020

Table 6 shows that majority of the respondents (159 representing 42.5 percent) and (154 respondents representing 41.2 percent) strongly agreed and agreed respectively that the networks has won the mind of it subscribers/dealers, while 48 respondents representing 12.2 percent and 13 respondents representing 3.5 disagreed and strongly disagreed that the network has won the mind of its subscribers/dealers.

Table 7 Respondent's opinion regarding the network's effort in building a sound relationship with subscribers/dealers

Survey statement	Degree of response	Percentage
My preferred network has done a lot to build a sound relationship with its subscribers /dealers	SA 122	32.6
	A 178	47.6
	D 61	16.3
	SD 13	3.5
Total	374	100.0

Source: Field work, 2020

Table 7 shows that majority of the respondents (122 representing 32.6) and (178 representing 47.6 percent) respectively said their preferred network has done a lot build a sound relationship with its subscribers/dealers, while (61 respondents representing 16.3 and 13 representing 3.5 percent) said their preferred network has done a lot to build a sound relationship with its subscribers/dealers.

Table 8 Respondents' network assessment in comparison with other networks

Survey statement	Degree of response	Percentage
I feel that the public relations unit of my network is better than others	SA 135	36.1
	A 105	28.1
	D 102	27.3
	SD 32	8.5
Total	374	100.0

Source: field work, 2020

Table 8 indicates that majority of the respondents (135 representing 36.1 percent) and (105 respondents representing 28.1 percent) respectively feel that their public relations unit is better than others. While (102 respondents representing 27.3 percent and 32 representing 8.5 percent) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that their public relations unit is better than others

Table 9 Level of contribution of network public relations unit to the enhancement of their subscriber-base

Survey statement	Degree of response	Percentage
The public relations unit of my network has contributed to the subscriber-base of my network	SA 117	31.3
	A 203	54.3
	D 45	12.0
	SD 9	2.4
Total	374	100.0

Source: field work, 2020

Table 9 shows that majority of the respondents (117 representing 31.3 percent and 203 respondents representing 54.3 percent) strongly agreed and agreed respectively that the public relations unit of their network has contributed to the subscriber-base of the networks. While (45 respondents representing 12.0 percent and 9 representing 2.4 percent) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that the public relations unit of their network has contributed to the subscriber-base of the networks.

Table 10 Impact of public relations on the success stories of the networks

Survey statement	Degree of response	Percentage
The services of the public relations unit of my network has undoubtedly contributed greatly to its success stories	SA 111	29.7
	A 190	50.8
	D 60	16.0
	SD 13	3.5
Total	374	100.0

Source: field work, 2020

Table 10 shows that majority of respondents (111 representing 29.7 percent) and 190 respondents representing 50.8 percent) strongly agreed and agreed respectively that the services of the public relations unit has undoubtedly led to increase in profit of the networks. While (60 respondent representing 16.0 percent and 13 representing 3.5 percent) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that the services of the public relations unit has undoubtedly led to increase in profit of the networks.

Table 11 Distribution of respondents on the networks public relations value on its operation

Survey statement	Degree of response	Percentage
My network public relations unit has added value to its operation	SA 105	28.0
	A 184	49.1
	D 71	18.9
	SD 15	4.0
Total	374	100.0

Source: field work, 2020

Table 4.1.10 shows that majority of the respondents (105 representing 28.0 percent and 184 respondents representing 49.1 percent) strongly agreed and agreed respectively that their network public relations unit has added value to its operation. While (71 respondents representing 18.9 percent and 15 representing 4.0 percent) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that their network public relations unit has added value to its operation.

Table 12 Level of subscribers' network affection derived from public relations units of the networks.

Survey statement	Degree of response	Percentage
The public relation unit of my preferred network has endeared its subscribers/dealers	SA 92	24.6
	A 192	51.3
	D 62	16.6
	SD 28	7.5
Total	374	100.0

Source: field work, 2020

Table 12 shows that majority of the respondents (92 representing 24.6 percent and 192 respondents representing 51.3 percent) strongly agreed and agreed respectively that the public relations unit of their preferred network has endeared its subscribers/dealers. While (62 respondents representing 16.6 percent and 28 representing 7.5 percent) disagreed and strongly disagreed that the public relations unit of their preferred network has endeared its subscribers/dealers.

1.24. Data presentation and analysis from in-depth interview: Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study. Mr A, will be used to represent GLO staff while Mr. will be used for MTN Staff.

- **Interview with Mr. A management staff**
- **Interview question 1: What is your knowledge of public relations in GLO Calabar?**
- My knowledge of public relations in GLO, Calabar is much, suffice to say that public relations is known by their activities.
- **Interview question 2: What would you say about the activities of public relations in GLO Calabar?**
- Public relations activities are targeted towards ensuring seamless and ease of communication
- **Interview question 3: What strategies do public relations unit adopt to achieve its goals in GLO Calabar?**
- Person to person, media campaigns via print, radio/ broadcasting, social media platforms etc.
- **Interview question 4: What is your assessment of the relationship between GLO and its publics?**
- Everywhere we exist, very cordial
- **Interview question 5: How would you assess the activities of public relations of GLO, Calabar in terms of its overall development of the organization?**
- It been totally beneficial and contributive to the sustenance of the business in Calabar and the general growth of the business.
- **Interview with Mr. B management staff**
- **Interview question 1: What is your knowledge of public relations in MTN Calabar?**
- I have good knowledge of public relations here

- **Interview question 2: What would you say about the activities of public relations in MTN Calabar?**
- Public relations’ activities are geared towards projecting a favourable image of the organization that is why the department of public relations in of MTN Calabar is very vital because it handles all forms of publicity.
- **Interview question 3: What strategies do public relations unit adopt to achieve its goals in MTN Calabar?**
- Public relations has lots of activities, ranging from corporate social responsibility strategy to give away items as prizes etc.
- **Interview question 4: What is your assessment of the relationship between MTN and its publics?**
- Cordial, with understanding and corporation.
- **Interview question 5: How would you assess the activities of public relations of MTN, Calabar in terms of its overall development of the organization?**
- It has been good so far.

1.25. Testing of Hypotheses

This section presents the results of statistical analysis of each of the hypotheses and research questions. The hypotheses were tested using population t-test (for a single test variable), simple linear regression and independent t-test analytical techniques. The research questions were answered through mean Responses to survey statements and descriptive percentages. All decisions regarding the hypotheses tested were taken at 0.5 level of significance such that a null hypotheses was rejected if the P-value associated with the computed test statistic was less than .05 and retained if the P-value was greater than or equal to .05. For each of the research questions assessing mean responses, a criterion mean (\bar{x}) of 2.5 was set for discussion.

1.26. Hypothesis one

1.26.1. *The level of corporate development of network companies (GLO and MTN) is not significantly high.*

This hypothesis was tested using population t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The test variable concerned here is the level of corporate development of network companies, while the test value or population mean is 0. The result obtained are presented in table 4.2.1

Table 13 Population t-test of the level of corporate development of Network companies

Variable	N	\bar{x}	SD	M (test value)	t-value	p-value
Contribution of public relations	374	15.150	2.601	0	112.638	0.000

Significant at .05 level. $p < .05$.

From table 4, the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05 (the level of significance for the test). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that, the level of corporate development of network companies (GLO and MTN) is significantly high.

1.27. Hypothesis two

1.27.1. *The role of public relations in network companies does not significantly predict their corporate development.*

To test this hypothesis, simple linear regression analysis was carried out with role of public relations (a continuous variable) as dependent variable. F-ratios test was used to test for the significance of the prediction. The result obtained are presented in table 4.2.2

Table 13 Regression of the corporate development of Network Companies on the Role of Public Relations.

R	= .236	Adjusted R-squared	= 0.053			
R - squared (R²)	=0.056	Std Error of Estimate	= 2.53121			
Source of variation	sum of squares	df	mean square	F-value	p-value	
Regression	140.194	1	140.194	21.881	0.000	

Residual	2383.421	372	6.407		
Total	2523.615	373			
Variable	standardized coefficient	standardized coefficient	t-value	p-value	
	Beta	Std Error	Beta		
Constant	11.904	0.706	0.236	16.860	0.000
Role of Public Rel.	0.208	0.044		4.67	0.000

In table 13 there is a positive relationship between role of public relations and corporate development ($r = .236$). This means, as role of public relations increases, corporate development also increases. R - Squared (R^2) of 0.056 implies that about 5.6% of the total variation in corporate development is accounted for by role of public relations. The P-value (0.000) associated with the computed F-value (21.881) is less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the role of public relations significantly predicts the corporate development of the Network companies.

To test for the significance of the regression coefficient (0.208), t-test was carried out. In both cases, the p-value (0.000 and 0.000), respectively are less than the chosen level of significance (0.05). This coefficient that both the regression constant and coefficient contribute significantly to the prediction of the corporate development of the network companies. The prediction equation can be written as:

$$Y = 11.904 + .208X$$

Where Y = corporate development

And X = the role of public relations.

1.28. Hypothesis three

1.28.1. *There is no significant difference in corporate development of GLO and MTN Calabar as opined by their lovers.*

Independent t-test analysis was carried out to test this hypothesis with Network companies of focus as independent variable and corporate development as dependent variable. The result obtained are presented in table 8.

Table 14 Independent t-test analysis of difference in corporate development between GLO and MTN as opined by their lovers

Network	N	\bar{x}	SD	test value	p-value
GLO	103	14.825	2.847	- 1.490	0.137
MTN	271	15.273	2.496		

From table 14 above, the p-value (.137) associated with the computed t-value (-1.490) is greater than the chosen level of significance (0.05). Consequently, the null hypothesis was retained. There is, therefore, no significant difference in the corporate development of GLO and MTN in the opinion of their lovers.

2. Discussion of findings

The discussion of findings done in this section of the research is in relation to the research questions directing this study:

2.1. Research Question 1: What is the impact of public relations on corporate development of MTN and GLO, in Calabar?

Table 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 plus interview question 5, combined to answer this question, it revealed that public relations has tremendous impact on corporate development. According to the findings, public relations has enabled or enhanced a

smooth relationship between the organization it represent (MTN and GLO) in Calabar with its public which has further has caused the network to be held in high esteem thereby, winning the mind of its publics. These have also made the teaming publics of the networks to consider the networks as better than others. Response to interview question 5 revealed that public relations activities are targeted towards ensuring seamless and ease of communication.

This is in line with view of Frank (1982, p.12) who argued that public relations is all forms of planned communication, outward and inward, between an organization and its publics for the purpose of achieving specific objectives concerning mutual understanding. **Research Question 2: To what extent does public relations contribute towards the level of awareness for corporate development of MTN and GLO in Calabar?**

Table 9, 10, 11, 12, 13 and interview question 2 combine to answer this research question as follows:

- The public relations unit have contributed to the subscriber-base of MTN and GLO in Calabar
- Public relations has contributed to the expansion of MTN and GLO in Calabar
- It has also led to increase in profit of MTN and GLO in Calabar
- It has also added more value to the operations of MTN and GLO in Calabar.

According to the interview, public relations has enormous functions which is meant at projecting a favourable image of an organization. This is in line with the views of oday (2014) who contended that public relations contribute positively in projecting a favourable image of an organization. Maduabuchi (2006) supported the views of Odey, that public relations is a tool for corporate development, it can influence the increase in company profit, influence on social responsibility, it can also enhance good customer relation impact on the brand image etc.

2.2. Research Question 3: What is the main source of network satisfaction among users of MTN and GLO?

Table 3 answers the question that MTN and GLO in Calabar derive their Network satisfaction from calls.

2.2.1. Hypothesis one

The level of corporate development of network companies (GLO and MTN) is not significantly high.

Table 1 and interview question 2 answered this hypothesis where the p-value (0.000) is less than .05 (the level of significance for the test). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that, the level of corporate development of GLO and MTN in Calabar is significantly high.

This is in line with the respond to in Interview question 2 which state that Public relations' activities are geared towards projecting a favourable image of the organization that is why the department of public relations in of MTN Calabar is very vital because it handles all forms of publicity

2.2.2. Hypothesis two

The role of public relations in network companies does not significantly predict their corporate development.

Table 2 provides answer to this hypothesis where there is a positive relationship between role of public relations and corporate development ($r = .236$). This means, as role of public relations increases, corporate development also increases. R – Squared (R^2) of 0.056 implies that about 5.6% of the total variation in corporate development is accounted for by role of public relations. The P-value (0.000) associated with the computed F-value (21.881) is less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the role of public relations significantly predicts the corporate development of the Network companies.

This is also in line the answer to Interview question 5 which states that the activities of public relations of GLO, Calabar in terms of its overall development of the organization is totally beneficial and contributive to the sustenance of the business in Calabar and the general growth of the business.

2.2.3. Hypothesis three

There is no significant difference in corporate development of GLO and MTN Calabar as opined by their lovers.

Table 4 provides answer to this hypothesis where the p-value (.137) associated with the computed t-value (-1.490) is greater than the chosen level of significance (0.05). Consequently, the null hypothesis was retained. There is, therefore, no significant difference in the corporate development of GLO and MTN in the opinion of their lovers.

3. Conclusion

The study's data and interpretations have led to the conclusion and agreement with the statement of Anyaogu as mirrored in the introduction of this work, that the extent of awareness and effectiveness of communication strategy generated as a result of the company's Public Relation's effort will reflect on company's profit, market share, works welfare, social responsibility and mutual understanding and good-will are essential for corporate development. Therefore, every organization require the contribution of public relations to enable it meet its full potential and achieve the goal which it was set for.

Recommendations

Arising from the findings and subsequent conclusion, the researcher has recommended the following:

- Public relations practitioners/professionals should embark on enlightenment campaign through the various media for proper understanding and implementation of public relations as a tool in achieving organizational objectives.
- To appraise public relations practice at various corporate organizations and such appraisal should be made public so as to encourage other organizations to imbibe public relations culture as a panacea for corporate development.
- A forum of chief executives of various organizations should be created to brainstorm on the development of public relations in Nigeria and its relevance in policy formulation and decision making.
- Public relations should as matter of necessity assume its rightful position alongside with other functions.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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